

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-1-22-IE-2%	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0
Vial:	22	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 1 22
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	10/11/2021 18:13:30 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 10:50:26 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.226	2744458	40.86	195596
2	9.869	2730504	40.65	143309
3	10.978	621271	9.25	34851
4	11.901	620249	9.23	39801

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-43-IE-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	47	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 2 43
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	300.0nm
Run Time:	19.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 300.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/8/2023 10:35:38 CST		
Date Processed:	3/21/2023 15:41:05 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.111	23951	0.19	1650
2	9.626	12006023	95.52	658505
3	10.751	207765	1.65	12002
4	11.339	331007	2.63	21668